

THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN FORMING THE STUDENT'S PERSONALITY IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Annotation: This article describes the role of innovative technologies in the formation of the student's personality in the process of primary education, and the ideas about the relevance of the lessons conducted on the basis of modern pedagogical technologies to the needs of the student's worldview and interests. Examples of innovative technologies used in primary education classes are presented.

Key words: innovation, education, student personality, technological map, intellectual potential.

Since primary education is the main link of general education schools, it is necessary to pay more attention to the perfect development of the student's personality in this process. One of the important tasks of today is the active use of advanced pedagogical technologies in the educational process, increasing the effectiveness of education, analysis and implementation. The responsibilities of elementary school teachers are endless. They accustom students who have just entered school to independent life and open the way to modern education. Children's attitude to study and mental potential are formed in this period. This also shows that the task of primary school teachers is responsible.

According to the methods of conducting lessons organized on the basis of pedagogical technologies, they should first of all meet the needs of the student. Because such lessons are closer to the psyche of the child. Achieving the goal based on arousing students' interest, desire and desire to learn learning materials is motivation, which is the internal rapprochement of the teacher and students.

It is of great importance to develop students' motivation to study in the primary school education process. Because the motive makes students interested in the educational process, encourages them to actively participate in the lesson and acquire knowledge. Interactive methods greatly help to develop the motivation to study. It should not be forgotten that it is necessary to take into account the age and level of knowledge of more children in primary classes. It will be good for them to pass lessons using simple, easy and time-consuming

game exercises. Activities connected with the environment develop children's mind, outlook, free thinking, expressive ability, and independent work skills.

The peculiarity of the use of innovative technologies in the course of the lesson is that they are implemented through the joint activities of the teacher and students. The teaching process includes the joint activities of the teacher and students. The pedagogue's task is to explain the educational material, increase students' interest in science, deepen their thinking and form their beliefs, guide students' independent activities, check and evaluate their knowledge, skills and abilities. A teacher who is devoted to his work is truly selfless.

A project of the lesson, that is, a technological map, is prepared in advance. In order to create a technological map, it is necessary to clearly define the activities of the teacher at each stage of the lesson, the ways of organization, management and activation of the teacher's pedagogic and educational activities of the students, and the time allocated for them. In the technological map, of course, there will be such principles as the organizational part, the motivation of the new topic, checking the knowledge of students, learning a new topic and strengthening it, analyzing the results achieved and making a conclusion. In this, the actions of the teacher and the student during the lesson are recorded step by step. The perfect structure of the technological map of the lesson allows you to implement goals and tasks, achieve efficiency and ensure coherence between stages, and use time effectively.

The elementary school period is the most important period in the formation of a child's personality. Elementary school students are gullible and susceptible to external influences. The main responsibility for forming positive emotions, qualities, and high moral standards in them falls on the primary school teacher. During this period, every word, every action, and influence of the teacher serves as a criterion of truth for the child. Because students strongly believe in teachers, listen to their opinions, and always follow their demands. A teacher teaching in primary school should have didactic skills. This means to clearly and clearly explain and easily deliver tasks such as writing, correct pronunciation of letters, repetition, and reading by adding syllables, which are considered difficult for them in the process of reading.

Especially a student who has just entered school expects encouragement and goodwill from his teacher. A teacher who can provide help and support for a student in the process of reading, learning to write letters, forming the process of performing arithmetic operations on numbers, by rationally organizing his didactic skills, lays the groundwork for the child's success in reading. Therefore,

it is important for the teacher to influence the students' psyche, to arouse positive emotions and to support their good intentions during this period when the child's psyche is experiencing anxiety, fear, and depression.

Today, life itself requires the wide introduction of innovative technologies in classes. The word "innovation" comes from the Latin word, which means renewal, change, innovation.

“Baliq skeleti” technology

This technology is demonstrated by drawing a fish model, in which the students try to reveal the problem in every way. A drawing of a fish skeleton is drawn on a piece of paper and the problem to be solved is written on its top. At the bottom, the ways to solve the problem are written. For example, in traffic lessons, on the topic "Rules of the road" "Why do you need a traffic light?" if given a problem, children enrich the fish skeleton with their thoughts.

Through this method, students learn to think independently, broadly, creatively, and critically.

“Venn diagrammasi” technology

This technology is one of the methods aimed at having one's own opinion about the topic taught in the native language and reading classes, working with the text, remembering the learned material, speaking, expressing one's opinion freely, and being able to evaluate all students by the teacher during the lesson.

In short, in a lesson with the effective use of innovative technologies, students will be able to fully demonstrate their abilities and capabilities, they will have the skills to work with a team, and they will learn to respect the opinions of others. This increases the efficiency of the lesson and serves to guarantee the quality of education.

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